

Kinetics of Reactions in Heterogeneous Systems.

Part I. The Reaction between Carbon Disulphide and Alkali.

BY DINAKAR KARVE' AND KRISHNAJI KHANDO DOLE'.

Investigations on the kinetics of liquid heterogeneous reactions are rare. Each reaction in the liquid-liquid system appears to have its own special characteristic and the measurement of the velocity is, in many cases, complicated by side reactions.

Carrarra and Zoppelari (*Gazzetta*, 1894, **24**, 364; 1896, **26**, 483) investigated the reaction between water on the one hand and sulphuryl chloride, thionyl chloride, phosphorus trichloride, phosphorus tribromide and phosphorus oxychloride on the other. Goldschmidt and Messerschmidt (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1899, **31**, 235) have studied the reaction of ethyl acetate dissolved in benzene with aqueous hydrochloric acid. They assumed that (i) the ester diffused very rapidly in both the phases, and (ii) that the reaction took place only in the aqueous phase. They showed that the monomolecular formula could be applied with a small correction for the counter reaction. Kremann investigated the hydrolysis of isoamyl acetate and of ethyl benzoate (*Monatsh.*, 1903, **26**, 315) and concluded that the velocity of the reaction, in the aqueous layer, is determined solely by physical factors like solubility, etc. A generally applicable rule for such reactions is thus not possible. Goldschmidt (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1900, **11**, 430), however, considers that the aqueous phase is saturated from the very beginning on account of the continuous agitation of the reaction mixture and that the velocity can be represented as that of an ordinary bimolecular reaction, or, if one of the reactants is present in excess, as that of a monomolecular reaction.

A large number of investigations* deals with the relation between the velocity and the rapidity of agitation (shaking or stirring).

* Sakurda (*Sci. Papers Inst. Phys. Chem. Res. Tokyo*, 1928 **8**, 21.); Fraenkel, Wengel and Cahn (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1928 **171**, 62); Bell (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, **32**, 892); Strauss and Hussey (*Ber.*, 1909, **42**, 2168); Titani and Kuran o (*Bull. Soc. Chem. Japan*, 1931 **6**, 152); Schwab and Knoell (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, **147**, 38); Klein (*Rocz. Chem.*, 1925, **6**, 101).

Reid and his co-workers (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1923, **15**, 1048; 1926, **18**, 535) have carried out important experiments in this connection.

We have investigated the reaction between carbon disulphide and alkali with and without non-aqueous solvents for the former, and also studied the effect of an addition of hydrogen peroxide on the velocity. The velocity of this kind of heterogeneous reaction must be divided into three parts, (i) the homogeneous reaction between the dissolved carbon disulphide and alkali; (ii) reaction between the undissolved carbon disulphide and the alkali at the surface of contact; and (iii) the reaction between the vapour of carbon disulphide and the aqueous alkali. In case no solvent is used for the carbon disulphide, the homogeneous reaction depends on the solubility in water of carbon disulphide and in case a solvent is used, on the distribution coefficient of carbon disulphide between the solvent and water. The second, *i. e.*, the liquid heterogeneous part of the reaction will further depend on the speed with which the resulting reaction products are removed from the surface of contact into the interior of the aqueous phase and the reactants brought from the interior to the surface of contact. The third part may be supposed to depend only on the speed of shaking and the alkali concentration, provided there is enough carbon disulphide to saturate the empty space in the bottle. Moreover, if one of these processes is very much slower than the others, it will be the factor on which the reaction velocity will mainly depend.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Procedure.—The reactants were mixed together in glass bottles shaken mechanically inside a cellar, where the temperature did not vary more than 0.1°. After a certain time the two layers in the reaction mixture were separated and the amount of combined sulphur present in the aqueous layer, which was a measure of the amount of reaction, was determined quantitatively. The quantitative analysis of the free and combined sulphur in the aqueous layer was carried out by the following method:

A known quantity of the separated aqueous layer was mixed with some fairly concentrated alkali solution in a beaker of about 400 c. c. capacity. (In case the alkali used in the experiment was concentrated enough, this addition is not necessary.) Bromine was then gradually added until a slight colouration was obtained and the oxidation was then carried to completion by the addition of concentrated nitric acid,

keeping the beaker cooled by means of cold water throughout the process. The excess of nitric acid was then driven off, in the usual way, the residue dissolved in water, a little hydrochloric acid and ammonium chloride added and sulphur estimated as barium sulphate. In the tables that follow, the carbon disulphide used up represents the amount thus obtained.

Solubility of carbon disulphide.—Solubility of pure carbon disulphide was determined in double distilled water at 26° and the value obtained 0.1634 g. in 100 c.c. of solution agrees well with that found by Rex (*Compt. rend.*, 1884, 99, 892, ; 1885, 100, 773).

The solubility of carbon disulphide in solutions of sodium chloride of different concentrations at 26° was also determined. The following table gives the results.

TABLE I.

Normality of NaCl soln. ...	0.0	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5
Solubility of CS ₂ ...	0.1634	0.1331	0.1115	0.0947	0.0832	0.0753
(g./100 c.c. soln.)						

Calculation of velocity constant.—In order to determine the velocity constant, the infinity values in the case of the reaction between carbon disulphide and sodium carbonate, as well as hydroxide, were determined. As the carbon disulphide was always in excess, we found by trial that 50.0 c. c. of N-NaOH used up 0.881 g. of CS₂.

Speed of shaking.—The speed of shaking was controlled by interposing a variable resistance before the shaking motor and three readings were taken, the speed being given in revolutions per minute. One revolution of the wheel is equal to one to-and-fro oscillation of the bottle. The same bottle was used for all the three experiments.

TABLE II.

N-NaOH = 50 c.c. CS₂ = 6.315 g. (5 c. c.), Time = 1 hr. Temp. = 24.6°.

Speed (R. P. M.) ...	129.5	147.5	164.6
CS ₂ used up (%) ...	3.207	3.794	3.977

It can be easily observed here that the increase is not directly proportional to the speed, the ratio of speed to the extent of reaction diminishing with increasing speed. No definite numerical relationship between the amount of reaction and the speed of shaking can, therefore, be deduced.

Temperature.—The speed here was kept constant.

TABLE III.

Amounts of reactants and time, same as in Table II.

Temp. ...	29°·0	31°·0	33°·5
CS ₂ used up % ...	5·137	5·946	7·160

The increase in the extent of the reaction is seen to be nearly proportional to the rise in temperature and is approximately 8% per degree; the decrease in solubility of carbon disulphide on rise in temperature has the effect of diminishing the temperature coefficient (Chancel and Parmentier, *loc. cit.*).

Total volume of the liquid.—The experiments were performed in three groups by varying the amounts of sodium hydroxide. Although the temperature differed for different groups it was constant for the experiments in one group. The speed of shaking was also kept constant. Amount of carbon disulphide and time are same as in Table II. Amounts in columns 2, 4 and 6 are intended to give an idea of the reaction per unit volume.

TABLE IV.

Temp. = 25°·20.			Temp. = 25°·7.			Temp. = 26°·5.		
NaOH used.	BaSO ₄ from 1 c.c. of aq. phase.	% of CS ₂ used up.	NaOH used.	BaSO ₄ from 1 c.c. of aq. phase.	% of CS ₂ used up.	NaOH used.	BaSO ₄ from 1 c.c. of aq. phase.	% of CS ₂ used up.
10 c.c.	0·03860 g.	0·9972 g.	30 c.c.	0·03196 g.	2·477 g.	50 c.c.	0·02849 g.	3·681 g.
20	0·03528	1·854	40	0·03194	3·301	100	0·02663	6·884
30	0·03512	2·723	50	0·03189	4·129	150	0·02564	9·940
			60	0·03168	4·911	200	0·02037	10·52

It is observed here that the total amount of reaction increases according to the increase of the amount of sodium hydroxide, the rate of shaking remaining constant.

The extent of the surface of contact will become smaller when the volume of alkali used goes beyond a certain limit on account of the smaller empty space available in the vessel. On the other hand, the

speed with which the reactants reach the surface of contact may be expected to increase on account of the increased total volume. The two effects are thus opposed to each other and the first is evidently more than compensated by the second, showing a net increase in the total amount of the reaction.

Concentration of alkalis.—In order to ascertain the relation between the concentration of alkali used and the extent of reaction, sodium hydroxide solutions of varying concentrations were shaken with carbon disulphide for different periods. The temperature was constant for one single group of experiments but differed for the three sets by one or two degrees.

TABLE V.

Sodium hydroxide

Amounts of reactants same as in Table II.

Time = 1 hr. Temp. = 25°		Time = 1 hr. Temp. = 25°		Time = 2 hrs. Temp. = 22°		Time = 3 hrs. Temp. = 24°	
NaOH.	% of CS ₂ used up.	NaOH.	% of CS ₂ used up.	NaOH.	% of CS ₂ used up.	NaOH.	% of CS ₂ used up.
0·1N	0·7127	0·5N	2·288	0·1N	1·003	0·1N	1·111
0·2	1·136	0·6	2·622	0·2	1·681	0·2	2·113
0·3	1·539	0·7	2·901	0·3	2·317	0·3	2·971
0·4	1·932	0·8	3·231	0·4	2·945	0·4	3·852
		1·0	3·841	0·5	3·526	0·5	4·666
				0·6	4·035	0·6	5·479
				0·7	4·423		

TABLE VI.

Potassium hydroxide.

Amounts of reactants same as in Table II. Temp. = 21·5°. Time = 1 hr.

N-KOH	...	0·1	0·2	0·3	0·4	0·5	0·6	0·7	0·8	0·9	1·0
% of CS ₂ used up	...	0·4597	0·8401	1·155	1·472	1·763	2·040	2·303	2·583	2·893	3·221

The results in the Tables V and VI show that the strength of alkali has a great influence on the reaction. For a change of concentration in sodium hydroxide from 0.1 to 0.28N, the extent of reaction is doubled, for a change from 0.1N to 0.7N it is four times and so on. The increase in the amount of reaction is seen to be proportional to the increase in the concentration of alkali solution.

Concentration of carbon disulphide.—Solutions of various concentrations in petroleum (b. p. 100°) were shaken with sodium hydroxide. The volume of the solution was 25 c.c. in all experiments. The volume of alkali was 50 c.c. of N-NaOH and the reaction was carried out at 27° for 1 hour.

TABLE VII.

Normality of CS ₂ ...	0.9387	1.785	2.573	3.217	3.834	4.399
% of CS ₂ used up ...	5.745	3.606	2.834	2.442	2.096	1.823

It has been already recorded by Sakurda (*loc. cit.*) that the surface exposed is proportional to the concentration of the reactants in heterogeneous systems. That conclusion is supported by the above results. The reaction however, is not directly proportional to the concentration of carbon disulphide. As the concentration of carbon disulphide increases, the actual amount used up also increases (although not proportionately), the percentage of the carbon disulphide used up as calculated from its total quantity present, however, diminishes with increasing concentrations. This is probably due to a greater consumption of sodium hydroxide with higher concentrations of carbon disulphide and consequently a rapid decrease in the strength of alkali. The decrease in the strength of alkali is greater, the higher the concentrations of carbon disulphide.

Change in the position of the vessel.—Two bottles of the same shape and capacity were taken of which one was kept vertical and the other horizontal in the shaking machine.

TABLE VII.

Amounts of reactants, same as in Table II.

Position of bottle.	% of CS ₂ used up.
Horizontal	4.205
Vertical	4.003

These experiments prove that in this particular type of shaking, the agitation is more vigorous in the horizontal position of the bottle.

Quantity of carbon disulphide.—Varying amounts of carbon disulphide from 0.1 c.c. to 10 c.c. were shaken with alkali. The experiments were carried out in two groups, the one group consisted of readings from 0.1 c.c. to 0.6 c.c. of carbon disulphide and other from 1.0 c.c. to 10 c.c. The temperature, the speed of shaking and the amount and concentration of the alkali were kept constant throughout one group of experiments.

TABLE VIII.

Amount of sodium hydroxide and time same as in Table II.

Temp. = 22.3°. Speed = 145 R. P. M. (average).			Temp. = 28.1°. Speed = 165 R. P. M. (average).		
Total CS ₂ .	CS ₂ used up.	% of CS ₂ used up.	Total CS ₂ .	CS ₂ used up.	% of CS ₂ used up.
0.1 c.c.	0.06987 c.c.	55.33	1.0 c.c.	0.3421 c.c.	27.08
0.2	0.1265	50.10	2.0	0.3469	13.73
0.3	0.1864	49.20	3.0	0.3510	9.264
0.4	0.1886	37.33	4.0	0.3550	7.026
0.5	0.1907	30.21	5.0	0.3595	3.655
0.6	0.1932	25.48	10.0	0.3654	2.894

The first three readings of the above table (column 2) show a rapid rise in the reaction from the addition of 0.1 c.c. to 0.3 c.c. of carbon disulphide. From the solubility of carbon disulphide in water, it is obvious that up to this point the reaction is a purely homogeneous one. With further addition of carbon disulphide, however, the aqueous layer becomes saturated and the two heterogeneous reactions (liquid—liquid and liquid—gas) also start. The above table shows that the heterogeneous parts of reaction do not consume any very large quantity of carbon disulphide and that the major part of the reaction takes place in the homogeneous system. Similarly, from the readings of the next group we can conclude that the addition of a large quantity of carbon disulphide does not influence the reaction to any very great extent. The homogeneous part of the reaction is evidently independent of the quantity of carbon disulphide if the latter is greater

than 0.3 c.c. It will then only depend upon the temperature at which the reaction is carried out. This may be one of the reasons of the sudden rise of the reaction velocity with a rise in temperature.

Addition of a neutral electrolyte.—The electrolyte used was sodium chloride. As the quantities of sodium chloride solution added were to be small, a 5*N* solution of the same was prepared. Similarly, the sodium hydroxide solution used was of 1.25*N*. The quantities used were adjusted in such a way that the ultimate quantity of sodium hydroxide used was 50 c.c. of 1.0*N* solution and the total volume of the aqueous phase was 50 c.c. In each case the experiment was performed in duplicate.

TABLE IX.

Amount of carbon disulphide and time same as in Table II.

Temp. = 23.5°. Speed = 139.3 R. P. M.			Temp. = 24.1° Speed = 146.6 R. P. M.		
Normality of NaCl.	CS ₂ used up.	% of CS ₂ used up.	Normality of NaCl.	CS ₂ used up.	% of CS ₂ used up.
0.0	0.2404 c.c.	3.807	0.0	0.2616 c.c.	4.143
0.2	0.2220	3.530	0.2	0.2417	3.828
0.4	0.2126	3.367	0.4	0.2299	3.642
0.6	0.2007	3.179	0.6	0.2187	3.463
0.8	0.1937	3.069	0.8	0.2071	3.280
1.0	0.1852	2.934	1.0	0.1963	3.110

The decrease in the reaction is seen to be proportional to the amount of sodium chloride added. The decrease is, as expected, due to the diminution of solubility of carbon disulphide in the aqueous phase.

Influence of addition of H₂O₂ with constant concentration of NaOH.—It appears from Table X that the effect of the addition of hydrogen peroxide to the reaction mixture is to increase the velocity of the same. This is probably due to the oxidation of some of the products of the reaction which decreases their concentration near the surface of contact. It is, therefore, equivalent to the carrying off of these products of reaction away from the surface of contact into the

interior of the aqueous phase. It was observed that, carbon disulphide and hydrogen peroxide alone do not react with each other. The addition of varying quantities of this substance to the reactants, increases the velocity of reaction in proportion to its concentration. With higher concentrations of hydrogen peroxide, the amount of alkali used up is quite considerable. This brings about a fall in the extent of reaction in the later stages.

Influence of addition of H_2O_2 with varying concentrations of both reacting substances has been shown in Table XI.

TABLE X.

Amounts of reactants and time, same as in Table II.

Temp. $23^{\circ}9$. = Speed about 137 R. P. M.

$H_2O_2(N)$...	0.0	0.08	0.16	0.24	0.32	0.40
CS_2 used up (c.c.)	...	0.2497	0.3701	0.5152	0.6292	0.7094	0.7771
% of CS_2 used up	...	3.955	5.862	8.081	9.965	11.24	12.31

TABLE XI.

Amounts of reactants and time, same as in Table II. Temp. = 29° .

NaOH conc.	H_2O_2 conc.	CS_2 used up.	% of CS_2 used up.
1.0N	0.0 N	0.3260 c.c.	5.17
0.909	0.045	0.3397	5.37
0.833	0.083	0.3728	5.29
0.769	0.115	0.4050	6.64
0.714	0.143	0.4283	6.77
0.660	0.166	0.4580	7.24

In general we can say that the action of hydrogen peroxide is proportional to the concentration used.

Comparison of the extent of reaction with sodium and potassium hydroxides.—Normal solutions of sodium and potassium hydroxides were shaken with carbon disulphide.

TABLE XII.

Amount of reactants and time, same as in Table II. Temp. = 26.8°

Alkali hydroxide.	CS ₂ used up.	% of CS ₂ used up.
Sodium	0.4788 c.c.	7.584
Potassium	0.5338	8.458

As is usual in generally all the reactions, potassium hydroxide seems to be more active than sodium hydroxide under the same conditions.

TABLE XIII.

Reaction between CS₂ in various solvents and aqueous NaOH.

Amounts of reactants and time same as in Table II. Volume of solvent = 10 c. c.

Solvent.	B.p.	Sp. gr. at 25°.	CS ₂ used up.
Petroleum ether	45°	0.670	5.981 %
Petroleum	100°	0.754	5.934
Toluene	110°	0.858	8.817
Xylene	138°	0.859	6.711
Monochlorobenzene	135°	1.1042	6.119
Monobromobenzene	175°	1.4856	5.654

TABLE XIV.

Comparison of the influence of concentration of carbon disulphide.

Amounts of reactants and time, same as in Table II. Volume of solvent = 25 c.c. Petroleum and xylene were used as solvents.

CS ₂ normality.	Petroleum at 25°	Xylene at 27°
	CS ₂ used up.	CS ₂ used up.
0.9387 N	5.745 %	6.764 %
1.785	3.606	4.338
2.573	2.834	3.343
3.217	2.442	2.746
3.834	2.096	2.334
4.399	1.823	2.004

The increase in the amount of reaction due to an increase in concentration is similar in both cases.

Velocity of Reaction between Carbon Disulphide and Alkali.

TABLE XV.

Carbon disulphide and aqueous sodium hydroxide.

Amounts of reactants same as in Table II. Temp. = 24.3°. $a = 5.400$ g. BaSO_4 .

Time.	Wt. of BaSO_4 x .	Wt. of CS_2 used up.	$a-x$.	K .
60 min	1.1595 g.	0.1892 g.	4.2405	0.00175
120	1.8815	0.3070	3.5185	0.00155
180	2.5290	0.4125	2.8710	0.00152
240	2.9915	0.4881	2.4085	0.00146
300	3.2715	0.5500	2.1288	0.00135
360	3.5135	0.5732	3.5135	0.00127

' a ' represents the total concentration of the alkali in 50 c.c. of normal solution in terms of barium sulphate in g.

The quantity of carbon disulphide employed was in sufficient excess since the 50 c.c. of $N\text{-NaOH}$ would use up only 0.881 g. of CS_2 . When the monomolecular formula is used for calculating the velocity constant, we get decreasing values of K .

TABLE XVI.

Carbon disulphide and potassium hydroxide.

Amounts of reactants, same as in Table II. Temp. = 24.7°. Speed = about 150 R. P. M. $a = 5.4$ g. of BaSO_4 .

Time.	Wt. of BaSO_4 x .	$a-x$.	K .
60 min.	1.6985 g.	3.7015	0.00273
120	2.6345	2.7655	0.00242
180	3.3122	2.0879	0.00229
240	3.8150	1.5880	0.00222
300	4.0575	1.3425	0.00201
360	4.1695	1.2305	0.00178

Here also the monomolecular formula is not applicable, indicating that the reaction is more complex.

Velocity of reaction between carbon disulphide and sodium carbonate.—Normal solutions of sodium carbonate were shaken with carbon disulphide for different periods and the value of K calculated. The values of K were seen to diminish rapidly on applying the monomolecular formula as in the case of the alkali hydroxides. The same thing happened when monochlorobenzene was used as solvent for CS_2 and NaOH was used as the alkali.

Carbon disulphide and sodium hydroxide with addition of hydrogen peroxide.—Dilute peroxide solutions of less than $0.5N$ strength were used. This presented deposition of sulphur., 40 c.c. of aqueous sodium hydroxide of $1.25N$ strength were taken and mixed with 10 c.c. of the above solution of hydrogen peroxide. The resultant normality of sodium hydroxide solution was $1N$, and that of hydrogen peroxide $0.1N$, the total volume of the aqueous phase being 50 c.c.

TABLE XVII.

$\text{CS}_2 = 6.415$ g. (5 c.c.). Temp. = 27.8° . Speed = 140 R.P.M.
 $a = 6.1$ g. of BaSO_4 .

Time.	BaSO_4 .	$a-x$.	K .
60 min.	2.070 g.	4.030	0.00300
120	3.655	2.945	0.00230
180	3.605	2.495	0.00216
240	4.020	2.080	0.00195
300	4.347	1.753	0.00181
360	4.596	1.504	0.00172

Here also the values of K calculated by the monomolecular formula diminish regularly. But the decrease becomes smaller and smaller as the reaction proceeds.

CONCLUSION.

It has been shown in the above experiments that in the case of the system between carbon disulphide and aqueous alkali, the velocity is dependent on the following factors :—

(1) Speed of agitation, (2) temperature, (3) total volume of liquid, (4) concentration of the alkali, (5) concentration of carbon disulphide when a solvent is used, (6) quantity of carbon disulphide (when no solvent is used).

Agitation has a two-fold influence, firstly that of increasing the surface of contact (and therefore increasing indirectly the effective velocity of reaction), and secondly of increasing the velocity with which products formed are removed from and fresh reactants brought to the surface of contact.

The velocity also depends on the method of shaking and the position of the vessel. The temperature coefficient, is rather high and corresponds to about 8 per cent. per degree rise in temperature.

Increase in the total volume of the alkali, the volume of the vessel remaining constant, decreases the empty space above the liquids. But this factor is apparently more than compensated by the increase in the speed with which the products are removed from and fresh reactants brought to the surface of contact, and also by the increase in the homogeneous part of the reaction, due to the larger quantity of carbon disulphide dissolved in the aqueous phase. Thus we have a net increase in the total amount of reaction. Increase in the concentration of the alkali causes a proportionate increase in the velocity of reaction. But the increase in the concentration of carbon disulphide (dissolved in an insoluble and neutral solvent) does not increase the reaction proportionately, for the higher concentration of carbon disulphide now uses up greater quantities of alkali and the concentration of the latter falls very quickly.

Increase in the quantity of carbon disulphide used has very little influence on the velocity of this reaction, for major part of the reaction takes place in the aqueous phase which is already saturated.

Potassium hydroxide is seen to be more active than sodium hydroxide under the same conditions.

The addition of a neutral electrolyte like sodium chloride decreases the reaction velocity, by decreasing the solubility of carbon disulphide. The heterogeneous part of the reaction is not affected.

When solvents are used for dissolving the carbon disulphide, the amount of reaction is seen to vary with the solvent. The reaction goes on diminishing in the order, xylene, monochlorobenzene, petroleum ether, petroleum, toluene, and monobromobenzene. This difference is not due to any one single physical property of the solvent. It may be due, among other things, to the partition coefficient of carbon

disulphide in the two solvents, and perhaps to the viscosity and density of the solvent which would determine the effect of agitation. Similarly it is observed that the change in the concentration of carbon disulphide in different solvents has the same effect on the reaction.

Addition of hydrogen peroxide increases the velocity by causing an increase in the velocity of diffusion of the reaction products into the interior of the aqueous phase. The action of hydrogen peroxide is proportional to its concentration, provided this latter is not excessive.

The reactions between carbon disulphide and aqueous sodium hydroxide, potassium hydroxide and sodium carbonate do not obey law for monomolecular reaction when one of the reactants, namely carbon disulphide is in excess. Nor is the bimolecular formula applicable when the reaction is carried out with varying finite concentrations of both the reactants. [The value of the velocity constants are seen to diminish regularly. The reaction is, therefore, a complex one as is also to be expected from the complex value of the products. On the addition of hydrogen peroxide, the values of K diminish to a very small extent to become nearly constant as the reaction proceeds further and further.

The reaction can be divided into three parts, *viz.*, (1) homogeneous reaction due to the appreciable solubility of carbon disulphide in water ; (2) the heterogeneous reaction at the surface of contact of liquid carbon disulphide and aqueous alkali; (3) and the heterogeneous reaction at the surface of contact of gaseous carbon disulphide and aqueous alkali. It is observed in the previous experiments that the major part of the reaction is due to (1). The reaction, therefore, is not so sensitive to agitation as a purely heterogeneous one would be. So also the temperature effect is partly neutralised by the decrease in solubility of carbon disulphide in the aqueous phase thus decreasing the reaction in the homogeneous system.